

Polyacetylenes and Terpenoids from *Erigeron karwinskyanus*

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Four mono- and fourteen sesqui-terpene hydrocarbons and all isomers of two acetylenic esters have been identified in the steam volatile oil of *Erigeron karwinskyanus* DC.

THE problem of insecticide resistance has necessitated research on new approaches. One of the promising methods is the use of naturally occurring antifeedants *i.e.* secondary plant metabolites which would be preferable because of their least harmful effect on the environment¹. The screening for the antimicrobial activity of various plant extracts has shown that the steam volatile oil of the plant *Erigeron karwinskyanus* possesses high activity against certain plant pathogens, *viz.* *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium* and *Fusarium* species². This prompted us to take up the chemical examination of the steam volatile extract of this plant. It was observed that the significant antimicrobial activity of the steam volatile oil of *E. karwinskyanus* is accredited to the naturally occurring acetylenic compounds in the oil. Cosmene, matricaria ester and a lactone have been identified in the oil of *E. karwinskyanus*³. In a previous paper⁴, we reported a new pyrone glucoside in the ethanolic extract of this species. However, no detailed study on the essential oil was reported. Present communication deals with polyacetylenic and terpenoid composition of the steam-volatile oil from the aerial part of *E. karwinskyanus* and variation of the yield and composition of oil from the different plant parts during different months.

Experimental

Plant material: The plants were collected locally and identified⁵.

Extraction of oil: The plants were collected at different stages of growth and divided into three parts, *viz.* leaves, stalks and flowers. After steam-distillation of each part separately, the essential oils were obtained by the extraction of the distillate with petrol (b.p. 40-60°). The ether extract was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was

removed to get essential oil. The oil from the complete aerial part was also extracted for the gc-ms analysis.

Analysis of oil: Si-gel was used for the column chromatography. Ir spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer 298 spectrophotometer. The oil was analysed by gc-ms using a Carlo Erba 2300 gas chromatograph (25 m×0.3 mm capillary column, FFAP phase) connected to a JEOL JN S-D 300 mass spectrometer with a data system JMA 2000. Mass spectra were recorded at 70 eV. The column temperature was 60° upto first 6 min, raised to 100° and programmed at 4°/min upto 200°. The injection, interface and ion source temperature were 250, 220 and 230°, respectively. The high resolution ms were measured at resolution 5000 and the methane was used as reagent gas in the CIMS study. For comparison of the change in composition at different stages of growth of the plant and in its different parts, the gc study of the oils under identical conditions was also carried out.

Results and Discussion

The maximum percentage oil yield in different plant parts is as follows: flowers (0.16, November), leaves (0.09, July), stalks (0.05, July) and complete aerial part (0.1, November).

The gc-ms study of the oil from the aerial part of the plant was carried out. The constituents were identified by comparing their ms with the published spectra⁶. Four monoterpene and fourteen sesquiterpene hydrocarbons, *viz.* β -pinene, myrcene, *trans*-ocimene, cosmene, α -copaene, γ -cadinene, β -cubebene, caryophyllene, β -elemene, humulene, γ -muurolene, *trans*- β -farnesene, α -cadinene, guaiene, δ -cadinene, bergamotene, *ar*-curcumene and *allo*-aromadendrene were identified (Table 1). Besides the terpenoids, the acetylenic esters were also

TABLE 1—GC-MS DATA ON MONO- AND SESQUI-TERPENE HYDROCARBONS

GC retention time min	Parent ion m/s	Important ions m/s	Compd.
1.3	186	93, 69, 121, 79	α -Pinene
1.4	136	41, 93, 69, 121	Myrcene
2.4	136	93, 121, 105, 80	<i>trans</i> -Ocimene
2.5	194	119, 91, 77, 105	Cosmene
6.3	204	105, 119, 161, 189	α -Copaene
7.9	204	161, 105, 91, 119	γ -Cadinene
8.9	204	161, 105, 91, 190	β -Cubelene
9.1	204	41, 93, 69, 133	Carvophyllene
9.2	204	81, 68, 93, 121	β -Elemene
11.0	204	93, 121, 147, 81	Humulene
11.3	204	161, 105, 91, 119	γ -Muurolene
11.8	204	69, 93, 81, 133	<i>trans</i> - β -Farnesene
12.0	204	161, 105, 110, 133	α -Cadinene
12.4	204	161, 105, 204, 189	Gualene
13.0	204	161, 134, 204, 105	δ -Cadinene
13.2	204	93, 119, 69, 135	Bergamotene
13.8	204	119, 132, 202, 145	<i>ar</i> -Circumene
19.4	204	51, 91, 161, 105	<i>allo</i> -Aromadendene

TABLE 2—GC-MS DATA ON ACETYLENIC ESTERS

GC retention time min	Parent ion m/s	Other fragment m/s	Compd.
3.1	176	147, 91, 161, 91	<i>cis</i> -Lachnophyllum ester
3.9	174	103, 159, 143, 77	<i>cis</i> -2- <i>cis</i> -8-Matricaria ester
4.8	176	147, 91, 119, 105	<i>trans</i> -Lachnophyllum ester
5.1	174	103, 159, 143, 63	<i>cis</i> -2- <i>trans</i> -8-Matricaria ester
6.1	174	159, 143, 103, 77	<i>trans</i> -2- <i>cis</i> -8-Matricaria ester
8.1	174	103, 159, 77, 143	<i>trans</i> -2- <i>trans</i> -8-Matricaria ester

identified. The fractionation of the oil by column chromatography over Si-gel gave a major fraction which showed ir bands at 2 235, 2 200, 1 735 and 1 175 cm^{-1} indicating it to contain polyacetylenic

esters. On gc-ms of this fraction, the electron-impact and chemical-ionisation mass spectra and high resolution mass spectra showed the presence of four acetylenic esters of molecular formula $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$ and two of $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$, indicating the presence of four geometrical isomers of 2,8-decadiene-4,6-diyonic acid methyl ester (matricaria esters) and two geometrical isomers of 2-decene-4,6-diyonic acid methyl ester (lachnophyllum esters), respectively (Table 2). The results show that the oil mainly consists of acetylenic esters, matricaria ester being the chief constituent, followed by lachnophyllum ester and sesquiterpene hydrocarbons. The monoterpenes constitute only a low percentage of the oil.

The gc analysis of the oils from flowers, leaves and stalks under identical conditions also indicate that the polyacetylenic esters are the major constituents of all the oils and are maximum in the flowers (in November) followed by the oil from the leaves and stalks.

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